

Transition towards environment friendly consumer products by co-creation of an oxidoreductase foundry

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Public Executive Summary of deliverable [D5.1: Liquid detergent formulation with novel oxidase-peroxidase cascade name of deliverable]

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Executive summary log

Submission	30-11-2024
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Main achievements/outcomes

Deliverable 5.1 concludes the work on one of OXIPRO's four innovation pillars, the detergent case. The specific objective of this case is validate 1 oxidase-containing liquid laundry detergent prototype for hygienisation

Liquid laundry detergent formulations have undergone significant advancements over time, enhancing their performance while minimizing environmental impact. The use of enzymes as detergent ingredients to effectively eliminate stains remove the need for excessive heat, employing milder temperatures (below 40°C) leading to energy savings (Commission Regulation (EU) 2019/2023). While liquid detergents capable of effective cleaning at 40 are readily available, the ability to achieve effective disinfection at lower temperatures remains the final challenge to be addressed. OXIPRO focused on alcohol oxidases, enzymes that produce antimicrobial hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) upon oxidation of alcohols, as a promising ingredient in laundry detergent to achieve disinfection at low temperatures.

The present report shows the progress of the detergent case study to develop a liquid detergent formulation containing alcohol oxidases to achieve disinfection at low temperatures. Glycerol oxidases were selected for its ability to generate H₂O₂ upon oxidation of glycerol, an ingredient commonly found in detergents. A thermally stable glycerol oxidase has been identified and engineered to obtain a variant with higher oxidation activity against glycerol (Santema et al., 2024). It has been demonstrated that under *in vitro* assay conditions, the oxidative action of the optimised glycerol

oxidase in combination with detergent ingredients can achieve complete bacterial eradication of gram positive and negative bacteria under laundry cycle relevant times and at low temperature conditions. Different liquid detergent formulations were explored to ensure stability of the selected oxidase. However, further developments are still required including, compatibility of OXIPRO glycerol oxidase with commonly used detergent enzymatic cocktails as well as development of liquid detergent formula that ensures long term stability of the selected enzyme.

References

Commission Regulation (EU) 2019/2023. (2019). Laying down ecodesign requirements for household washing machines and household washer-dryers. Official Journal of the European Union, L 315, 285–322. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2019/2023/oj>

Santema, L., Rotilio, L., Xiang, R., Tjallinks, G., Guallar, V., Mattevi, A., Fraaije, M.W. (2024). Discovery and Biochemical Characterization of Thermostable Glycerol Oxidases. *Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology* 108(1):1-14.